

**SPORTS IN THE SYSTEM OF PHYSICAL CULTURE OF SOCIETY
INSTITUTIONAL APPROACH**

Umarova Zulkhumor Urinbayevna

Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan

Associate Professor of the Department of Sports and Outdoor Games

Umarova Diyora Zafarjon qizi

students of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan

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Annotation. The article deals with the study of the problem, the organization of modern social production with its mechanization and automation of production processes, is characterized not only by a decrease in the share of physical labor, but also its different rhythm, increasing complexity and intensity. In addition to the sociological analysis of new scientifically based forms, means and methods of physical education, corresponding to the requirements of scientific and technological progress, is currently the most important task of the theory and practice of physical culture movement.

Keywords: Problem of development, modern social, production, process, reduction, increase in physical labor, sociological analysis, new scientifically based forms, means, method, physical education, scientific and technological progress, mass physical culture, big sport, healthy lifestyle, sport phenomenon.

The organization of modern social production with its mechanization and automation of production processes is characterized not only by a decrease in the proportion of physical labor, but also by its different rhythm, increasing complexity and intensity. This inevitably requires significantly greater tension of mental, mental and physical strength, increased coordination and culture of movements, and high concentration of attention from workers and specialists. The listed qualities need constant development and improvement, since the more advanced the technology and the more complex the production technology, the more perfect the person managing them must be.

The sociologically based use of physical culture and sports in the process of preparing workers for specific types of work is becoming increasingly relevant. Therefore, sociological analysis of new scientifically based forms, means and methods of physical education that meet the requirements of scientific and technological progress is currently the most important task of the theory and practice of the physical education movement.

This situation dictates the search for alternative ways to organize human life, form a culture of health-forming human activity using effective means and

methods of physical culture. Today, the role of health is considered and assessed by specialists, at best, as a biological component, an environmental factor, a determinant of a person's working, living, and leisure conditions, and not a system of his own active activity, socially oriented toward the constant strengthening of the vital forces of the body and maintaining its functionality.

Thanks to the achievements of science and technology, medicine has largely saved people from the danger of a number of infectious diseases and given them various methods and means of treating diseases. At the same time, the twenty-first century has brought a decrease in the volume of human physical activity, an increase in neuropsychic and other types of stress, chemical pollution of the external and internal environment and other negative phenomena associated with scientific and technological progress.

The lifestyle of a modern person is characterized by physical inactivity and hypokinesia, overeating, information overload, psycho-emotional overstrain, drug abuse, etc., which ultimately leads to the development of so-called diseases of civilization. The prevalence of smoking, alcohol and drug use among schoolchildren and students indicates that existing methods of creating a healthy lifestyle culture have not yet produced the desired results.

The effectiveness of existing methods of hygiene education used both at school and in the family requires significant adjustment. From a sociological point of view, the phenomenon of sport, currently defined as a specialized area of social life activity associated with identifying and demonstrating the physical capabilities of people, as well as physical culture (a sphere of social activity aimed at promoting health and developing a person's physical abilities) are closely interrelated with indicators of population health and its valeological well-being.

According to the Ministry of Sports, physical education and sports for the younger generation, which is the country's sports reserve, have become almost inaccessible. More than 2/3 of students in secondary schools practically do not engage in sports, which, coupled with poverty, wars and social ills that have struck the country, has had an extremely negative impact on the health of young citizens.

5 million young citizens have chronic pathology, 642 thousand are disabled children. The phenomenon of the development of physical culture in the context of sociological analysis is most often determined through value orientations. Currently, both mass physical culture and "big sport" in our country do not live up to social expectations and are going through a period of crisis.

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The current situation is largely a consequence of the insufficient development of the sociology of physical culture, the social aspects of this type of human culture, and sometimes a one-sided focus on the physical development of the individual. The interest of sociologists in solving problems of the development of the phenomena of physical culture and sports from the standpoint of their institutionalization in the development of the essential forces of the individual is determined by many circumstances.

Modern civilization is significantly transforming the environment, social institutions, and man himself. In this regard, physical culture is assessed not only as a source of social innovation, but also as a means of transforming the very nature of HUMAN (*Homo sapiens*) as a social individual. From here it becomes clear the desire of modern researchers to identify the potential of social institutions of society associated with the reproduction of its physical culture, to find its internal reserves and new opportunities for the effective management of sociocultural processes.

This “inconsistency” is a consequence of the socio-economic cataclysms that our society has experienced and continues to experience in the last three to four decades. At the same time, in the context of the country’s transition to a new era of state construction, there is an urgent need for a scientific analysis of social functions in the development of the sphere of physical culture in general and sports, in particular, not only in a particular region, but also from the standpoint of the general provision of the civilized reproduction process public life of the country.

The works of G.E. are devoted to the analysis of the place and role of physical culture and sports in the organization of leisure and recreational activities, the realization of creative potential, and the development of the essential forces of the individual. Zborovsky, L.N. Kogan, G.P. Orlova, B.C. Tsukerman and others. The foundations of institutional theory were laid at the turn of the 19th-20th centuries. works of G. Spencer, E. Durkheim, M. Weber, T. Veblen, T. Parsons. G. Spencer is the founder of the doctrine of social institutions. E. Durkheim and M. Weber made a certain contribution to the development of the theory of social institutions.

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